

Possible Anticancer Agents: I. Synthesis of Some Substituted Amides from *p*-Fluoroaniline and 2-Aminopyridine

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In an attempt to synthesize compounds similar to 2-chloro-4',4''-di-2-imidazolin-2-yl-terephthalanilide dihydrochloride (I, R = Cl), other similar compounds (I, R = H, NO₂)²⁻⁴, the corresponding imidazolin isophthalanilide (II)⁵ and 1,4-bis(3-bromopropionyl)piperazine NSC-25154 (Str. III)⁶, a number of amides derived from *p*-fluoroaniline and 2-aminopyridine have been prepared with a view to test their anticancer and other biological activity. The

synthesis consists of condensing the primary amines with chloroacetyl chloride to get the corresponding chloroacetylamino derivatives, which are further reacted with piperidine, morpholine and piperazine to get the desired amides.

where X = piperidino, morpholino and piperazino moiety.

EXPERIMENTAL

N-Chloroacetyl-*p*-fluoroaniline (IV, a), m.p. 129–130° was prepared by the action of chloroacetyl chloride on *p*-fluoroaniline in 85 per cent yield⁷.

2-Chloroacetylaminopyridine (IV, b), m.p. 122–124° was obtained by treating 2-aminopyridine with chloroacetyl chloride⁸. The yield was poor (33%).

N-Morpholinoacetyl-*p*-fluoroaniline : A mixture of 2 g. of IV-a and 1.9 g. of morpholine in 20 ml. of absolute ethanol was refluxed for 5 hr. The reaction mixture was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure. The resulting gummy material was washed with a solution of sodium bicarbonate and finally with water. The product was recrystallized from ethanol to give 2.2 g. of the compound (88% yield), m.p. 91°. *Anal.* Calc. for C₁₂H₁₅FN₂O₂ : C, 60.5; H, 6.3; N, 11.8. Found : C, 60.7; H, 5.9; N, 11.4.

The hydrochloride of the base was prepared by dissolving it in dry benzene and saturating the solution with dry HCl gas. It was filtered and recrystallized from ethanol, m.p. 195°. *Anal.* Calc. for C₁₂H₁₆ClFN₂O₂, H₂O : C, 49.2; H, 6.1. Found : C, 49.4; H, 6.0.

N-Piperidinoacetyl-*p*-fluoroaniline was similarly prepared from 4 g. of IV-a and 3.6 g. of piperidine in 40 ml. of absolute ethanol. The residue was purified as above and finally recrystallized from ethanol to give 4.2 g. of the compound (84% yield), m.p. 80°. *Anal.* Calc. for C₁₃H₁₇FN₂O : C, 66.1; H, 7.2. Found : C, 66.6; H, 7.4.

The hydrochloride was likewise prepared and recrystallized from ethanol, m.p. 181°. *Anal.* Calc. for C₁₃H₁₈ClFN₂O, $\frac{1}{2}$ H₂O : C, 55.4; H, 6.7. Found C, 55.2; H, 6.6.

1,4-Di (*p*-fluorophenylacetamido)piperazine dihydrochloride : To a solution of 2 g. of IV-a in 20 ml. of absolute ethanol, was added 4.6 g. of piperazine and the resulting mixture was refluxed for 10 hr. Evaporation to dryness as usual, gave a semisolid mass, which could not be crystallized. It was dissolved in dry benzene, the solution dried (anh. CaCl₂) and saturated with dry HCl gas. A solid separated, which was filtered, dried and recrystallized from ethanol-water (2 g., 83%), m.p. 248°d. *Anal.* Calc. for C₂₀H₂₄Cl₂F₂N₄O₂, H₂O : C, 50.1; H, 5.4. Found : C, 50.4; H, 5.4.

2-Piperidinoacetylaminopyridine : A mixture of 3 g. of IV-b and 3 g. of piperidine in 40 ml. of dry benzene was heated under reflux for 5 hr. Reaction mixture was filtered to remove piperidine hydrochloride formed during the reaction. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure and the product was recrystallized from ethanol (3 g., 87%), m.p. 160°. Even after several purifications good analytical results were not obtained

The dihydrochloride was prepared as usual and recrystallized from ethanol, m.p. 230°d. *Anal.* Calc. for C₁₂H₁₉Cl₂N₃O, 2H₂O : N, 12.8. Found : N, 13.0.

2-Morpholinoacetylaminopyridine dihydrochloride : 2-Morpholinoacetylaminopyridine was prepared from 3 g. of morpholine and 3 g. of IV-b in 45 ml. of dry benzene. As the resulting mass was gummy, its hydrochloride was prepared by the usual procedure and

recrystallized from ethanol (yield 4.5 g., 88%), m.p. 240°d. *Anal.* Calc. for $C_{11}H_{17}Cl_2N_3O_2$: N, 14.3. Found : N, 14.1.

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